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Anomalous Transport Behaviour During Electrolysis

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WHEN a solution of a salt such as sodium sulphate is electrolysed, equivalent amounts of alkali and acid as expected get liberated at the cathode and the anode respectively, each being also equivalent to the current passed. We checked it up and found it to be true at room temperature and nearabout. However, at a higher temperature of about 40° onwards the results are totally unexpected and this is reported in this note.

Experimental

The electrolysis cell is a simple U-tube (30 cm high, 32 mm O.D.) immersed in a thermostat with arrangements for draining out liquid from different levels on one side, the other side being then kept stoppered. The electrodes are platinum foils (1 cm × 1 cm) or platinum wires (1 cm) inserted from the top. The electrolytes are either sodium or potassium sulphate solutions of varying strengths ($10^{-2} N$ to N). We passed 10 mA current through the electrodes for about 2 hr and drew off the cathode solution and titrated it. We verified that chemical changes take place under this condition upto a depth of about 6 to 8 inches or so from the top to a gradually decreasing extent.

Results and Discussion

The results are presented graphically in Fig. 1. The most striking observation is that with an increase in temperature the alkali liberated decreases very considerably, so much so that at 60° it is ~5% of the expected amount. The alkali liberated at the cathode at room temperature is almost equal to the theoretical amount, but it falls far short of the theoretical value at 40° and more so at 60°. This sharp change with temperature can be convincingly demonstrated, though in a qualitative manner by removing from time to time a little solution with a dropper from near the cathode and testing it against phenolphthalein or a universal indicator in an experiment similar to the "polarity test". At room temperature a positive test is obtained within

Fig. 1

0.5 min whereas at 60° there is hardly any positive response even after 10 min. With a similar cell but with arrangement for separate collection of the cathode gas and the anode gas¹ we verified that these gases are explosive mixtures in agreement with previous report² from this laboratory. However, the total volume shows a considerable deficit at room temperature but the deficit gets almost wiped out at the higher temperature.

Theory: This surprising result is difficult to understand against the well-accepted Hittorf idea of ion migration. The solution contains Na^+ and SO_4^{2-} ions to an extent about a million times that of the H^+ and OH^- ions. If we imagine a partition at the middle, any movement of Na^+ ions and SO_4^{2-} ions across this partition should lead to liberation of acid and alkali. Since the acid-alkali liberation is observed to be very much inhibited, the compelling conclusion appears to be that the current conduction is predominantly not through Na^+ and SO_4^{2-} ions under this condition. The alternative idea of electronic conduction cannot be true because in that case there will be no gas liberation to a proportionate extent. Actually gases get amply liberated both at the cathode and at the anode. Both the gases are highly explosive mixtures of hydrogen and oxygen and the total amount is only slightly less than that prescribed by Faraday's law. The real problem is to find a mechanism which is not accompanied by chemical decomposition but allows for gas liberation (even mixtures) at the two electrodes. We believe that charged clusters of water molecules, $(\text{H}_2\text{O})_x^+$ at the anode and $(\text{H}_2\text{O})_y^-$ at the cathode, form and these species take more and more part in current conduction with increase in temperature. These species break down after moving for some distance, liberating oxygen and hydrogen respectively ($\text{H}_2\text{O}^- = \text{H} + \text{OH}^-$, $\text{H}_2\text{O}^+ = \text{H}^+ + \text{OH}$). When such decomposition of H_2O^- takes place in the

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anode compartment anodic hydrogen is obtained; H_2O^+ decomposing in the cathode compartment is responsible for the observed oxygen at the cathode. An encounter with an oppositely charged ion particularly H^+ and OH^- ions may also cause the same kind of gas liberation at the wrong electrode. Details are none too clear but the results oblige us to think that there must be some other concurrent kind of mechanism of current conduction different from that proposed by Hittorf which is responsible for these anomalous observations; this latter mechanism is probably connected with ions derived from water. It is quite likely that this hitherto unknown mechanism is responsible for the fact³ that explosive mixtures of hydrogen and oxygen are liberated at both cathode and anode on electrolysis of sodium or potassium sulphate solutions at higher temperature even for strong solutions at fairly high current density.

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Synthesis of Cyclohepta[b]Thiophen Derivatives. Part-II

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OVER the last twenty years there has been a growing interest in the use of 2- and 3-substituted thiophenes in medicinal chemistry¹. Raney nickel desulphurization of thiophenes has also been developed as an important tool for the synthesis of aliphatic compounds². In connection with our programme on dehydrogenation studies of spiro compounds having a cycloheptane ring³ and on desulphurization reaction, several cyclohepta[b]thiophen derivatives were needed. Here we report the synthesis of 5,6,7,8-tetrahydro-6,6-spirocyclohexane-4H-cyclohepta[b]thiophen-4-one (7), 5,6,7,8-tetrahydro-6,6-spirocyclohexane-4H-cyclohepta[b]thiophen (10) and their alkyl derivatives by an adaptation of the method developed earlier⁴. Recently, synthesis and photochemical behaviour of cyclohepta[b]thiophen-4-ones were reported⁵.

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Friedel-Craft condensation of cyclohexane-1,1-diacetic anhydride with thiophen gave the keto acid (1) which was reduced by Huang-Minlon procedure to the pentanoic acid (4). The acid chloride of the reduced acid was cyclised using stannic chloride to give the cyclic ketone (7). The cyclic ketone was reduced by Huang-Minlon procedure to the spiran (10). In a similar manner, 5,6,7,8-tetrahydro-2-methyl-6,6-spirocyclohexane-4H-cyclohepta[b]thiophen (11) and 5,6,7,8-tetrahydro-2-ethyl-6,6-spirocyclohexane-4H-cyclohepta[b]thiophen (12) were synthesised starting from appropriate alkylthiophen and cyclohexane-1,1-diacetic anhydride. The structures of the keto acids (1-3) and cyclohepta[b]thiophen-4-ones (7-9) were confirmed by spectral and analytical evidences.

Experimental

Alkyl thiophenes⁶ were prepared by the method indicated. Light petroleum refers to the fraction, b.p. 60-80. Ethereal extracts were dried with anhydrous sodium sulphate. Analytical data of the compounds (1-12) were all within experimental error.

3,3-Cyclohexane-5-(2-thienyl)-5-oxopentanoic acid (1): To a vigorously stirred solution of thiophen (21 g; 0.25 mole) and cyclohexane-1,1-diacetic anhydride (45.5 g; 0.25 mole) in nitrobenzene (200 ml) at 0° was added anhydrous aluminium chloride (63 g; 0.5 mole) slowly in parts. The mixture was stirred further for 1 hr, hydrolysed with ice and hydrochloric acid, and steam distilled to remove the solvent. The crude product after filtration was dissolved in sodium carbonate solution, charcolised and finally acidified with conc. HCl. The solid product was obtained by filtration and on recrystallisation from light petroleum gave the keto acid (1), m. p. 103° (46 g, 69%). ν_{max} (KBr): 1640 and 1690 cm^{-1} ; δ : 1.4 (10H, s), 2.7 (2H, s), 3.1 (2H, s), 7.2 (1H, m), 7.7 (2H, m) and 11.2 ppm (1H, s).

3,3-Cyclohexane-5-(2-thienyl) pentanoic acid (4): The keto acid (1) (13.3 g; 0.05 mole) was reduced by Huang-Minlon procedure⁷ using diethylene glycol (56 ml) potassium hydroxide (9.87 g) and ~99% hydrazine hydrate (10.7 ml). The pentanoic acid (4) distilled at 190/0.7 mm and slowly solidified, m.p. 75° (7.9 g, 62.7%).

5,6,7,8-Tetrahydro-6,6-spirocyclohexane-4H-cyclohepta[b]thiophen-4-one (7): To a solution of 4 (13.86 g; 0.055 mole) in ether (50 ml), purified thionyl chloride (8.8 ml) and pyridine (several